

Synthesis and Reactions of a 4-Methyl-3-(3'-thione)-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylcoumarin

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Various substituted triazoles have recently received significant importance because of their diverse pharmacological properties¹. The present work reports the synthesis of some heterocyclic compounds containing triazolethione and benzopyranone moieties because such compounds are expected to show pharmacological activity.

In continuation of our studies on coumarin derivatives², we have prepared 4-methyl-3-(3'-thione)-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylcoumarin (2) in order to establish the reactivity of the carbonyl groups of the α -pyrone and the thione group of the triazole rings toward some nitrogen nucleophiles and carbon electrophiles. Compound 2 was prepared via condensation of 4-methyl-3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin (1) with thiosemicarbazide in boiling pyridine. The formation of 2 may proceed by the initial nucleophilic attack of the amino group to the ester carbonyl without attack at the carbonyl of the α -pyrone ring followed by cyclisation (Scheme 1).

It has been reported³ that the α,β -unsaturated- α -pyrone ring in coumarin derivatives is not opened by primary amines, while the action of hydrazines caused the heterocyclic ring opening of coumarin⁴. The reaction of compound 2 with hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine gave the corresponding 4-methyl-3-(3'-hydrazinyl)-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylcoumarins (3a,b) (Scheme 1). The condensation of 3a with aromatic aldehydes, namely, benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde in boiling acetic acid yielded the corresponding 4-methyl-3-(3'-arylidenehydrazonyl)-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylcoumarins (4a, b).

Alkylation of compound 2 with alkyl halides, namely, methyl iodide and ethyl iodide in the presence of sodium ethoxide afforded the corresponding 4-methyl-3-(1'-alkyl-3'-alkylthio)-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylcoumarins (5a, b). The presence of thione-thiol equilibrium in compound 2 promoted us to study the behaviour of the active thiol group towards

activated olefinic bond such as acrylonitrile in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate under Michael reaction condition to give 4-methyl-3-[3'-(2'-cyanoethylthio)]-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylcoumarin (6).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 spectrometer using solutions in hexadeuteriodimethyl sulphoxide and tetramethyl silane as internal standard.

Compound 2: A mixture of 4-methyl-3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin (0.01 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol) in pyridine (50 ml) was refluxed for 15 h. The mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-water, neutralised with dilute HCl (10%) and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (50%); ν_{\max} 1 695 (α -pyrone CO), 3 280–3 175 (NH), 1 625 (C=N), 1 615 (C=C) and 1 180 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.9–8.3 (4H, m, ArH), 9.7 (1H, br, SH ratio 44.6) and 10.1, 11.3 (2H, br, NH and NHC=S ratio 55.4).

Compounds 3a, b: A solution of compound 2 (0.01 mol) and hydrazine derivatives, such as hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The hot reaction mixture was filtered, then cooled and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (3a)/petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (3b), (50/35% yield); ν_{\max} 1 690–1 696 (CO), 1 615 (C=N) and 3 390–3 185 (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.2 (2H, br, NHNH), 6.8–7.9 (9H, m, ArH) and 10.5 (1H, br, cyclic NH).

Compounds 4a, b: A mixture of 3a (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde or anisaldehyde (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The hot reaction mixture was then filtered, cooled and the resulting

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–6*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Colour
2	170	Pale yellow
3a	190	Yellow
b	85	Orange
4a	260	Yellow
b	285	Yellow
5a	230	Pale yellow
b	205	Pale yellow
6	220	Yellow

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S (for 2, 5, 6) analyses.

solid was dried and crystallised from acetic acid, (60–65%); ν_{max} 3 295–3 240 (NH), 1 690 (CO) and 1 625–1 615 cm^{-1} (C=N); 4a δ (CF_3COOD)

2.2 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.7–8.7 (11H, m, ArH, N=CH and NH) and 10.5 (1H, br, cyclic NH).

Compounds 5a, b: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and alkyl halides (namely, methyl iodide or ethyl iodide) (0.02 mol) in sodium ethoxide solution (30 ml; 0.005 g-atom sodium/25 ml absolute ethanol) was heated for 6 h, then cooled, poured into dilute HCl (1%) and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (53–55%); ν_{max} 1 715 (CO) and 1 625 cm^{-1} (C=N); 5a δ ($\text{CF}_3\text{-COOD}$) 2.1 (3H s, CH_3), 2.5–3.2 (6H, s, N- CH_3 and S- CH_3) and 6.9–8.0 (4H, m, ArH).

Compound 6: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and acrylonitrile (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g, 0.02 mol) was heated for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice/10% HCl mixture and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol,

NOTES

(60%) ; ν_{\max} 1 695 (CO), 1 625 (C=N), 2 215 (C≡N) and 3 205 cm^{-1} (NH) ; δ (CF₃COOD) 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.2 and 4.4 (4H, 2xt, CH₂CH₂), 7.0–8.2 (4H, m, ArH) and 10.05 (1H, s, NH).¹¹

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